

TRIAL PRODUCTION AND EVALUATION OF HONEYCOMB FROM GFRP

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ABSTRACT

We tried to prepare the pre-preg composed of glass fiber and thermosetting resins (phenolic, unsaturated polyester and epoxy resins), and these honeycombs were prepared by expansion method, and their mechanical properties were evaluated. When the compressive strength were considered concerning the cell size, these honeycombs were similar to those of aluminum ones. When the compressive strength was examined as a function of the density, these honeycombs were less than 30 % of aluminum one in the strength.

INTRODUCTION

Honeycomb is constituted of many hexagons that are prepared by adhering films. This structure is very light in weight, and the volume of 95~99 % is occupied by air. Honeycomb core is ordinarily used in sandwich construction by adhering aluminum, GFRP, or CFRP panel on both sides. The honeycomb sandwich constructions have many advantages such as low weight, high strength [1], excellent resistance to impact damage [2], and effective heat-exchange [3]. Honeycombs were invented 50 years ago and have been utilized in various fields. In early days, paper and aluminum honeycombs were developed. Recently, a honeycomb using aramid fiber was developed. This one is very light in weight and excellent on the compressive strength. However the honeycombs are very expensive, and are only a limited usage. In this study, we tried to prepare the honeycombs composed of glass fiber and the thermosetting resins, i. e., phenolic, unsaturated polyester and epoxy resins, and their mechanical properties were evaluated.

PREPARATION OF GFRP HONEYCOMB

In this study, first, we prepared the GFRP per-preg, and, second, honeycomb was prepared from that.

PREPARATION OF PRE-PREG

Pre-preg means the material which is semihard FRP. Namely the fiber is impregnated with the resin mixed with hardener and is slightly cured. Pre-preg is easy for preparing honeycombs. Glass fiber was HS180 supplied by Asahi Fiber-Glass Ltd.(Tokyo, Japan). This is a roving cloth in which glass fiber is woven in a right angle. We adopted three thermosetting resins, i. e., phenolic, unsaturated polyester and epoxy resins. In the case of phenolic resin, the main ingredient was MZ-F4, an acid catalyzer was PX-33 and a latent catalyzer was CR85-50, all of these materials were supplied by Dainippon Ink and Chemicals Ltd.(Tokyo, Japan). In the case of unsaturated polyester, the main ingredient was Rigolak R-802 and the hardener was CH50, all of these materials were supplied by Showa Shell Sekiyu K. K.(Tokyo, Japan). In the case of epoxy resin, the main ingredient was Epikote #828 which was supplied by Konishi Ltd.(Osaka, Japan), the hardener was methyl-3,6-endomethylene-1,2,3,6,-tetrahydro phthalic anhydride MHAC-P which was supplied by Hitachi Chemical Industry Co. Ltd.(Tokyo, Japan) and the accelerator was 2E4MZ which was supplied by Shikoku Chemical Industry Co., Ltd.(Tokyo, Japan). We used silanecoupling agent for increasing adhesive strength between glass fiber and resin. KBM603 was for phenolic and epoxy resins. KBM503 was for unsaturated polyester. These silanecoupling agent were supplied by Shin-Etu Chemical Ltd.(Tokyo, Japan).

The process of preparing GFRP pre-preg is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Process for preparing GFRP pre-preg.

The preparing method of GFRP pre-preg is as follows; 1. cutting off a roving cloth to a length of 140 mm × 140 mm. 2. dipping the roving cloth in the water for ten minutes to remove the binder on the roving cloth. After that, the roving cloth was dried in an oven. 3. dipping the roving cloth in the water solution of the silanecoupling agent. After that, the roving cloth was dried in an oven. 4.

mixing a resin with hardener in the ratio shown in Table 1. 5. dropping the resin to the roving cloth placed on a teflon sheet, and extending the resin on the roving cloth. 6. removing air in the impregnated roving cloth with a vacuum pump for one hour. This process also promotes the impregnation of the resin into the roving cloth. 7. heating the impregnated cloth under pressing. The components, curing temperature and curing time for various resins are shown in Table 1. 8. cooling the pre-preg in the air.

Table 1. Component, curing temperature and curing time for various resins in the preparation of pre-peg.

	Phnolic resin	Unsaturated polyester	Epoxy resin
Component	MZ-F4:PX-33:CR85-50 =100:1:0.4	R-802:CH50 =100:2	#828:MHAC-P:2E4MZ =100:100:1
Curing temperature (°C)	60	80	80
Curing time (min)	10	10	10

PREPARATION OF HONEYCOMB

A corrugation and an expansion methods are well known for preparing honeycombs [4]. In this study, we adopted the latter one for GFRP honeycomb core, because of easy process for this material. Adhesive material was applied on a film in some width at a given interval, and many films were accumulated and stuck together (Process[I]). These films are expanded gradually (Process[II]).

Figure 2. Process for preparing GFRP honeycomb.

The process of preparing GFRP honeycomb core is as follows; 1. cutting off the pre-preg film to a length of 12.7mm which corresponds to the thickness of honeycomb core " T ". 2. application of adhesive on the pre-preg film in the width " a " at a given interval. The phenolic adhesive PR22 was for phenolic resin and epoxy adhesive material Bond E Set for unsaturated polyester and

epoxy resins. All these adhesives were supplied by Konishi Ltd.(Osaka, Japan). 3. sticking many pre-preg films, where teflon sheet were placed between adhered areas for preventing adhesion. 6. hardening the adhesive material. In the case of the pre-preg of phenolic resin, stacked films was kept at 80°C for one hour. In the cases of unsaturated polyester and epoxy resin, stacked films were left them for a few days. 5. expanding them and keeping at a given temperature for several hours, as shown in Table 2. 6. cooling it in the air. And then cutting in the size of the test specimen. Curing temperature and curing time for preparing honeycombs are shown in Table 2. Length of adhered area, length of teflon sheet and number of films are shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Length of adhered area, length of teflon sheet and number of films in each cell size.

Cell size (mm)	Length of adhered area (mm)	Length of teflon sheet (mm)	Number of films (ply)
12	6.9	20.8	12
18	10.4	31.2	8
25	14.4	43.3	6

Table 3. Curing temperature and curing time for preparing honeycombs.

	Phenolic resin	Unsaturated polyester	Epoxy resin
Curing temperature (°C)	110	100	150
Curing time (min)	10	120	60

Figure 3. Symbols for honeycomb core.

Fig. 3 shows a part of an ordinary honeycomb core. In the honeycomb core, the " L direction " means the film direction, the " W direction " the one perpendicular to the film direction [5], the " T " the thickness of the honeycomb core, " C " the cell size which means the distance between two faces next each other. Other, and " a " the width of the adhered area calculated by Eqn(1).

$$a = \frac{C}{2\sin 60^\circ} \quad (1)$$

EVALUATION OF GFRP HONEYCOMB

JIS A 6931 [6] and MIL STD 401B were adopted for the evaluation of the honeycomb. JIS A 6931 is concerned only with a paper honeycomb core. MIL STD 401B, which is a standard of United States Army, is very popular and has been applied to aluminum honeycomb. In this study, the latter method was adopted mainly for the evaluation of GFRP honeycomb.

COMPRESSIVE TEST

MIL STD 401B useful for the determination of compressive strength of GFRP honeycomb [7]. Compressive strength means the maximum load divided by the cross section area in compression [2]. Compressive strength is obtained from Eqn. (2):

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P_c}{A} \quad (2)$$

where σ_c is the compressive strength; P_c the maximum load, and A the the cross section area of the test specimen.

Test is carried out by placing the test specimen between two steel plates, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Apparatus for compressive test of honeycomb core.

The size of the test specimen is 50 mm × 50 mm in cross section and 12.7 mm in thickness. The test speed is 2.0 mm / min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Compressive load-strain curves of various honeycombs are shown in Fig. 5. The strains at the maximum compressive loads of ordinary honeycombs are 1~5 %. But, that of GFRP honeycomb is 30 %. It is larger than that of ordinary honeycombs. This will be caused by the reason why GFRP honeycomb crushes gradually at the creases in the roving cloth.

Figure 5. Strain dependence on compressive load for various honeycombs. These data were obtained in our laboratory.

- GFRP honeycomb core
- Aluminum honeycomb core
- · - · - · Aramid honeycomb core

The compressive strengths of GFRP honeycombs are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The compressive strengths of an aluminum honeycomb [8], an aramid honeycomb [9] and CFRP honeycomb are shown in them. In Fig. 6, the compressive strengths were plotted against the cell size of honeycomb core. In Fig. 7, the compressive strengths were plotted against the density.

Figure 6. Cell size dependence of compressive strength for various honeycombs.

- | | | | |
|---|----------|---|------------------------------|
| ■ | CFRP | ○ | GFRP (Phenolic resin) |
| ▼ | Paper | □ | GFRP (Unsaturated polyester) |
| ◆ | Aramid | △ | GFRP (Epoxy resin) |
| ▲ | Aluminum | | |

Figure 7. Density dependence of compressive strength for various honeycomb cores.

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|---|----------|---|------------------------------|
| ■ | CFRP | ○ | GFRP (Phenolic resin) |
| ▼ | Paper | □ | GFRP (Unsaturated polyester) |
| ◆ | Aramid | △ | GFRP (Epoxy resin) |
| ▲ | Aluminum | | |

As shown in Fig. 6, these honeycombs are similar to those of aluminum ones. However, it is expected that GFRP honeycombs are stronger in compressive strength than that of aluminum, though the experimental points in small cell size were not obtained. Especially, the honeycomb prepared from epoxy resin is excellent. When the cell size was 25 mm, the compressive strengths

of honeycomb cores from unsaturated polyester and from phenolic resin were 73 % (0.19 MPa) and 65 % (0.17 MPa), respectively, as compared with that from epoxy resin (0.26 MPa). However, when the cell size was 12 mm, the strength of that from unsaturated polyester and from phenolic resin were 75 % (0.66 MPa) and 33 % (0.29 MPa), respectively, as compared with that from epoxy resin (0.88 MPa). The smaller the cell size becomes, the larger the difference of compressive strength is. This will be caused by the reason why the adhered area with adhesive becomes relatively smaller than that expected in the small cell size, when honeycombs were prepared from unsaturated polyester and phenolic resins.

When we compare honeycombs as a function of the density, GFRP honeycombs are inferior to those of ordinary honeycombs. The compressive strength of that from phenolic resin and unsaturated polyester or epoxy resin were 10 % and 30 % , respectively, as compared with that from aluminum. This will be due to the fact that the GFRP honeycomb breaks at a crease which is the weakest part in the roving cloth.

CONCLUSION

We prepared the pre-preg composed of glass fiber and thermosetting resins, i. e., phenolic resin, unsaturated polyester and epoxy resin. Honeycombs were prepared from the pre-preg by expansion method. Their mechanical properties were evaluated mainly according to MIL STD 401B. The compressive strengths of GFRP honeycombs were equal to or stronger than those of ordinary ones in a given cell size.

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